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Higher education in state universities in Sri Lanka – review of higher education since colonial past through international funding for development

Abstract

Purpose – The purpose of this paper is to review historical developments in higher education in Sri Lanka, and review issues faced and strategies adopted to improve higher education in state universities in the country. The paper also reviews national and international forces that influenced to modernise and improve higher education in state universities in the country.

Design/methodology/approach – The paper reviews available published documents from the last two decades to present and discusses key national and international forces transforming the higher education of the country and strategies adopted to modernise and improve higher education in state universities in the country.

Findings - Historical development in general and higher education together with key characteristics of the Sri Lankan education system are discussed. The governing bodies of the state university education, donor agencies and strategies adopted for the development of higher education in the country during the recent history have been reviewed. Conclusions and challenges for the future are also presented.

Originality/value – The higher education of the country underwent rapid transformations over the past seven decades with the aim of strengthening the wider relationship between university, industry and society. A review on higher education in Sri Lanka could provide lessons valuable for academics and practitioners alike worldwide.

Key words Higher education, higher education policy, development of higher education, Sri Lanka.

Paper type Research paper

Introduction

Higher education is facing changes aimed at strengthening the wider relationship between universities, industry and society. However, state funded higher education institutions are at the centre of attention with regard to where this relationship between universities, industry and society is located and played out (Gunter and Fitzgerald, 2013). Despite the pressures of reduced budgetary allocations, changing priorities in government strategies, public accountability and complexities of higher education institutions themselves, the state has a responsibility to ensure a smooth operation of its higher education system. Over the recent decades the highest emphasis was on quality control with governments demonstrating greater accountability in the use of state funds (Abankina et al., 2012; Milliken and Colohan, 2004). As a consequence, changes were made to the structure and funding of higher education, where increased competition for students and subsequent resources were prominent among higher education institutions (Milliken and Colohan, 2004). Accordingly, higher education institutions face pressures from external and internal forces to change (locally and/or internationally) and redefine their identity and delivery balancing the imperatives of quality and relevance (Hall et al., 2013; Milliken and Colohan, 2004).

The focus of this paper is to review higher education in state universities in Sri Lanka. However, irrespective of the country or region where it is located, the relevance of programmes on offer and quality and effectiveness of higher education has been questioned fundamentally in recent years (Dyllick, 2015; Pfeffer and Fong, 2004). This implies that recent pressures on higher education are neither specific nor distinctive to Sri Lanka. As Dyllick (2015, p. 18) states “there are serious doubts about [higher education institutions’] ability to provide students with the skills needed to function ... in modern organisations and to prepare them for the professional demands and challenges of globalised business in a pluralistic world”. To face challenges, higher education institutions need to capitalise on significant opportunities available (Hall et al., 2013). However, the way countries respond to these challenges may be different and may have historical origins (Anyanwu, 2013; London, 1995; Ranasinghe, 1992). During the recent history of Sri Lanka, it had been a colony of Portuguese, Dutch and British for several centuries from 1505 to 1948. The country’s general (primary and secondary) education as well as higher education were formalised with the establishment of missionary schools by the Portuguese for propagating Roman Catholic religion, by the Dutch through the Dutch Reformed Church, and by the British through more broad-based approach to education compared to the prior colonisers. As a result, like

education systems of other British colonies at that time (London, 1995), Sri Lankan education system largely found expression within the general framework of British colonialism. The content of the formal education, administrative procedures and management practices of the country were strongly influenced by the British colonial ideology. The higher education was limited to the teaching of subjects in humanities with the belief in a ‘generalist’ administrator for the public services of the colony (Ranasinghe, 1992). This is in parallel to the goals of education in the British colonies across the Asia, Africa, and West Indies at that time (Anyanwu, 2013; London, 1995; Ranasinghe, 1992).

During the recent past, the Sri Lankan education system, which is predominantly public with state authorities running most primary and secondary schools and higher education institutions, is undergoing rapid transformations. The strategies of transformation in higher education aim to strengthen the wider relationship between university, industry and society. Although the state provided education is free of charge, and equity is protected by providing equal access to the education, the education sector (especially, higher education sector) is criticised for its quality and relevance in responding to increasing challenges in local and global spheres. Therefore, it is important to understand strategies adopted to meet these demands, and how attitudinal changes are introduced in the higher education system (with specific focus to state universities) to bring about greater accountability and responsiveness in terms of relevance and quality.

In the above context, the purpose of this paper is to review historical developments in higher education in the country, and review issues faced and strategies adopted to improve higher education in state universities in the country. In doing so, based on the studies of selected policy documents from the last two decades, this paper also reviews key national and international forces transforming the higher education of the country and strategies adopted to modernise and improve higher education in state universities in the country.

The article is organised as follows. The next section provides a review of literature relevant for the paper followed by a brief account on the country- Sri Lanka. Thereafter, historical development in general education and higher education together with key characteristics of the Sri Lankan education system are discussed. This is followed by a discussion on governing bodies of the state university education, and donor agencies and strategies adopted for the development of higher education in the country. This section elaborates how ideas connected to higher education reforms have been introduced and interpreted by the governments of Sri Lanka together with International Development

Association/World Bank. Conclusions and challenges for the future are discussed in the last section.

Education under colonial rule

Formal education in colonies originated and found expression within the framework of their colonial masters (London, 1995; Megarrity, 2005; Fergusson and Masson, 1997). Although education was an integration of practical learning with religious and cultural instruction of the independent territories prior to become a colony, in the advent of colonialism education was formalized along colonial ideology (Fergusson and Masson, 1997) and educational matters were largely conducted by Christian missions (Megarrity, 2005). Hence, the content of education programs and administrative procedures and management practices used to deliver the programs were crafted based on colonial ideology. However, colonial masters emphasized narrow vocational skill outcomes for indigenous people and did not expect indigenous educated elite to gain much influence and power in that era (Megarrity, 2005).

After regaining independence although these countries expanded their secondary and tertiary education, these countries faced continual shortage of skilled manpower for national development and cohesion a future nation (Megarrity, 2005). Since independence these countries faced immense challenges in educational reforms (Hanson, 1998; Ikoya, 2007), and the role of national political context in education reforms is difficult to ignore (Fry and Bi, 2013; Anyanwu, 2013).

Higher education reform

If higher educational institutions to fulfil their educational, research and informational functions, they should be able to respond to changing education and skill requirements of the nation and adopt flexible modes of organisation and operation in the rapidly changing higher education landscape (Donnelly, 2004). Education challenges in the developing countries were mainly include non-availability, inadequacy and dysfunctionality of formal structures, inadequate funding, inadequate representation of donor agencies and low productivity of the systems (Ikoya, 2007). During the recent past, policy makers, academics and administrators involved in higher education identified the need of policy reforms in ideologies in higher education, governance and management, financing, teacher professionalism as well as modernizing, improving and liberalizing higher education (Abankina et al., 2012; Donnelly, 2004; Lanford, 2016; Liu, 2016; Møller and Skedsmo, 2013; Zhao and Qiu, 2012).

When considering improvements in higher education outcomes, challenges in preserving the quality of education has been widely cited (Abankina et al., 2012; Holmes, 2008; Møller and Skedsmo, 2013). The quality of higher education impacts on producing more talents and high quality talents in workforce (Abankina et al., 2012; Holmes, 2008; Zhang et al., 2012; Zhao and Qiu, 2012).

Higher education systems that are publicly funded are undergoing rapid transformations to redefine the relationship between the state, universities and civil society (Estad et al., 2014; Gunter and Fitzgerald, 2013). In the context of decreasing funding from the state and greater public accountability for educational spending, higher education institutions are increasingly becoming complex institutions to manage. Financial optimization (Abankina et al., 2012), preserving equity by providing equal access (Møller and Skedsmo, 2013) and transparent accountability (Donnelly, 2004) have become key components of education development strategy.

Recent years has also witnessed an increase in the influence of market forces on higher education (Donnelly, 2004). Countries initiated reforms aimed to reduce government funding for higher education while increasing the exposure of higher education to competitive market forces (Donnelly, 2004). As a part of this strategy, countries sought assistance of donor agencies and experts to advise on higher education reforms (Wang and Berquist, 2003). For example, the World Bank has taken the initiative to introduce customized strategies for the development of higher education in various nations (World Bank Group, 2011; Wang and Berquist, 2003). It offers policy options for developing countries to reform education systems to meet the needs of the knowledge economy.

Sri Lanka - country background

The Democratic Socialist Republic of Sri Lanka is an island situated in the Indian Ocean at the base of the Indian Sub-Continent. Sri Lanka is a country with a unique and a proud historical record of an impressive civilisation and a culture of achievements spanning over a period of several centuries before Common Era (Sri Lanka Tourism Development Authority, non-dated [n.d.]). During the recent history of Sri Lanka, the country had been under the Western rule (Portuguese, Dutch and British) for several centuries. A Portuguese colonial mission, first, arrived to Sri Lanka in 1505 followed by the Dutch and British. Sri Lanka regained independence in 1948. Still, the country remained a dominion in the British Commonwealth of Nations until 1972. In the year 1972 the country has been declared a Democratic Socialist Republic. The country inherited its economic, political and

administrative structures mainly from the British rule, which lasted over hundreds of years. At the time of regaining independence Sri Lanka was mainly an agricultural economy, where largely foreign owned, export oriented plantation crops sector (i.e., tea, rubber and coconut) existed side by side with a predominantly small holding peasant agricultural sector. The economy was open to free trade, and it was fully integrated to the global economic system through exports and imports (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 1998). Since the adoption of trade and investment liberalisation policies in 1978, the economic growth has been driven mainly by the private sector led expansion of services and manufacturing industries.

Today, Sri Lanka is at the threshold of middle-income status currently rated as a lower middle income country with a population of around 20 million people (World Bank, 2011b). Sri Lanka's strategic location on the seaways between the East and West is an advantage to the island's positioning in global logistics. Policy makers in Sri Lanka promote economic growth of around five key hubs, namely, knowledge, ports and shipping, aviation, commercial and energy. Still, the World Bank (2011b), states:

The knowledge hub is considered central to the transformation of the economy, as knowledge is the key ingredient of growth in the modern global economy, and provides the foundation for the success of all the other hubs, ... and Sri Lanka as a middle income country will depend on knowledge-intensive activities such as banking and finance, information technology, communications, insurance, and hospitality and leisure services. (World Bank, 2011b, p. 1)

Sri Lanka needs to develop its intellectual and human capital to compete successfully in the knowledge-intensive world. Higher education system of the country should be able to produce professionals, scientists, technocrats, managers and administrators, who are well-educated, skilled, and enterprising and innovative.

Sri Lankans enjoy adult franchise since the early 1930s, and this has made them active participants in a multi-party democratic political process. As the welfare of the citizens played a significant role in the elections and in maintaining political stability, successive governments were relatively committed to welfare (Ahmed and Ranjan, 1995; Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 1998). These efforts contributed to reduce the incidence of poverty, which is reflected in the achievement of outstanding human development indicators and Millennium Development Goals (United Nations Development Programme, n.d).

However, country's slow growth in economic performance in the past was largely due to the thirty years of war experienced by the country until May 2009 (Ahmed and Ranjan,

1995; World Bank, 2011b). In this regard, higher education sector can play a key role in promoting democratic values, the celebration of multiple cultures and respect for diversity and social tolerance through the scholarship, teaching, research and advocacy of the universities (World Bank, 2010).

Method

The study took an interdisciplinary approach and focused on complex relationships between economics, politics and culture in changing the nature of higher education in Sri Lanka, and the reforms introduced to enhance identity, quality and relevance of higher education. The main data collection method used in this study is the review of secondary data published during the last two decades. As stated earlier, by doing so this research attempted to present historical developments in higher education in Sri Lanka, and review issues faced and strategies adopted to modernize and improve higher education in state universities in the country. To achieve these objectives policy and other related documents such as statistical reports published in journals, books, working papers and newspapers were reviewed. With regard to higher education reform, documents published by the national government (e.g., National Education commission, Central Bank of Sri Lanka, and University Grants Commission) and the World Bank were the main sources of information. The information obtained from the review were classified in terms of the sources and content of data as these were used in the secondary sources of information reviewed.

Findings and discussion

This section provides findings of the secondary data review under two main headings in accordance with the objectives of the study. These two main heading were historical developments and governance of higher education and higher education reforms in Sri Lanka. The section on higher education reforms reviews issues faced and strategies adopted to improve higher education in state universities in the country with the assistance of World Bank from 2003 to 2015.

Historical developments and governance of higher education in Sri Lanka

In the ancient society, education was associated with Buddhist temples. There were places of learning that can be compared to present day universities, which were run by Buddhist Clergy, who integrated practical learning with religious, philosophical and cultural

instruction. These institutions also gave opportunity for male lay students to receive education (Ministry of Human Resource Development, Education and Cultural Affairs, n.d.)

In 1505, Portuguese conquered the coastal areas of Sri Lanka and these areas remained captured for 150 years. Portuguese introduced and established missionary schools with the sole intention of propagating Roman Catholic religion (Ministry of Human Resource Development, Education and Cultural Affairs, n.d.). Dutch, who succeeded the Portuguese, took steps to expand the education by promoting religion through the Dutch Reformed Church. The British succeeded the Dutch in early 19th century and introduced a dual system of education, which consisted of the state assisted schools in the English medium for the elite and schools in the vernacular for common people. In parallel to these education systems introduced by each of the three Western rulers, the Buddhist religious schools also existed in the country (Ministry of Human Resource Development, Education and Cultural Affairs, n.d.). However, published documents on these historical developments are rare to be found.

In 1931, a semi-autonomous government was established in the country by the British. Sri Lanka had a numerous achievements in education sector during the period of 1931-1947, prior to regaining independence in 1948. One of such achievements include the enactment of the Education Ordinance of 1939, which still remains as the basic law of education in Sri Lanka, and introduced free education from the kindergarten to university (Ministry of Human Resource Development, Education and Cultural Affairs, n.d.). After regaining independence, further improvements were made to increase the access to general education.

The secondary education of the country consists of two public examinations, namely, General Certificate of Examination- Ordinary Level at age 16 after 11 years of schooling and the General Certificate of Examination- Advanced Level at age 18 after 13 years of schooling. The results obtained at the General Certificate of Examination- Advanced Level examination determine the eligibility to enter into state universities for higher education. Gender parity is high in the education system, with equal proportions of females and males enrolled in primary education and a slightly higher number of females than males enrolled in both secondary and higher education (World Bank, 2010). As a result, the country provides the highest level of access to primary and secondary education in South Asia, and ranks high among developing countries in terms of gender development and gender empowerment (World Bank, 2010).

However, Sri Lanka under-invests in education compared to other middle income and developing countries. The World Bank (2010, p. 27) reports that Sri Lanka invested 2.8 per

cent of gross domestic product (GDP) in education and this percentage was well below 4.3 per cent devoted in average by the class of lower-middle income countries to which Sri Lanka belongs. Further, South Korea, Malaysia and Thailand, whose economic performance is of interest for Sri Lankan economic policy, invest over 4 per cent of GDP and between 15 per cent and 28 per cent of government expenditures on education (World Bank, 2010).

Higher education in Sri Lanka. When considering the early beginnings of higher education, the Colombo Academy, which was the leading secondary school in the country, was affiliated to the University of Calcutta in 1859. Renamed Royal College, it became the first 'college' to provide some form of higher education and prepared students for external examinations conducted by the University of London. In 1870, the Ceylon Medical School was established; it was elevated to the status of a college in 1880. In 1889 the Licentiate in Medicine and Surgery offered by this college was recognised by the General Medical Council of United Kingdom. In 1921, the Ceylon University College was established in Colombo as an affiliated institution of the University of London. In 1942, University of Ceylon was established by absorbing the two higher educational institutions of Ceylon Medical College and Ceylon University College. However, during this pre-independence era access to higher education was limited to very few from affluent families (Tilakaratna, 1997). The higher education of the country expanded rapidly over the past seven decades after the introduction of free education system since 1945.

At present, the Ministry of Higher Education and University Grants Commission of Sri Lanka (referred hereafter as University Grants Commission), which was established under the University Act of 1978, govern the state funded university system of the country. The main focus of governments' higher education development up to about 2005 was on the expansion of the state university system, in particular the establishment of a university in every province (total of nine provinces) of the country. This policy objective has been reached, and now Sri Lanka has 15 state universities under Ministry of Higher Education and University Grants Commission with at least one state university for each province. One of the main tasks of University Grants Commission is allocating new intakes for Bachelor's degrees in state universities based on the capacity of each university and students' performance at the General Certificate of Examination- Advanced Level examination. Considering disparities in the distribution of educational facilities at district level, the University Grants Commission adopts a policy of combining merit system as well as district basis quota system in determining the number of students entre into each stream of study in each university. This

policy facilitated access to state universities for students from working class and lower income families. Accordingly, 50 per cent of students enrolled in state universities came from underprivileged families. Although higher education in Sri Lanka can be identified as an important avenue for social mobility, the total expenditure of state provided university education as a percentage of total government expenditure was 1.66 per cent in 2013, which is less than 0.5 per cent of GDP; the universities depend on this state funding to meet about 96 per cent of their annual expenditure (University Grants Commission, 2014).

In contrast to very high levels of general education enrolment in Sri Lanka, which consists of primary and secondary education, the full-time enrolment in higher education in state universities was less than 2 per cent of the age group. This was less than the average in South Asia (8 per cent) and far below than the East Asian countries that Sri Lanka seeks to emulate such as Malaysia (11 per cent), Thailand (20 per cent) and Singapore (34 per cent) (World Bank, 2010). Still, the number of students enrolled in higher education increase in every year. This increase in enrolment can be attributed to both demand and supply side factors. On the demand side, a steady increase in the number of students completing secondary education led to increase the number who sought opportunities for higher education. In addition, the growth of Sri Lankan economy led to increase household income, and willingness of parents to pay for higher education whether within the country at private sector higher education institutions or overseas. On the supply side, the number of both state owned and private sector owned higher education institutions have expanded increasing the enrolment capacity of higher education institutions (World Bank, 2010). However, these private higher education institutions were established under the Company Law of Sri Lanka, and Ministry of Higher Education and University Grants Commission do not have purview over these institutions. Further, these private higher education institutions have never received the status of the state universities and not referred to as universities in the country.

In general, slightly more than half of the students enrolled in state universities are female. The number of female students enrolled in state universities is higher in subject areas such as law, humanities, architecture, dentistry, veterinary science and business studies. In terms of higher education enrolment by the type of institution and mode of delivery, Sri Lankan higher education sector has about 390,000 students enrolled, of which full-time undergraduate student enrolment in state universities as internal candidates accounted for 19 per cent, undergraduate student enrolment in state universities as external candidates accounted for 58 per cent, distance mode undergraduate student enrolment at the state owned Open University of Sri Lanka accounted for 7 per cent, and postgraduate enrolment in state

universities accounted for 2 per cent (World Bank, 2010, p. 26). The balance 22 per cent enrolled in alternative fee levying higher education sector, which includes state owned Sri Lanka Institute for Advanced Technological Education as well as private sector owned higher education institutions that offer degrees and diploma and certificate level job-oriented qualifications (World Bank, 2010).

There were 5439 teachers (from Lecturer probationary, Lecturer, Senior lecturer, Associate Professor to Professor) engaged in the state university system in 2013 and the student-teacher ratio was 17.8 in 2013 (University Grants Commission, 2014). With regard to the development of university teachers, the first ever staff development centre in state universities was established in 1997 at the University of Colombo with the accreditation of Staff and Educational Association of United Kingdom. To date, it has trained over 2000 teachers from all state universities across Sri Lanka. Overtime, all other state universities have established their own centres since it is now mandatory to address the development needs of teachers. The University Grants Commission provides financial assistance for teachers (on probation) to undertake doctoral studies at local and overseas universities. In addition, National Center for Advanced Studies in Humanities and Social Sciences, which was established under the Universities Act of 1978 for the purpose of promoting advanced studies and research mainly in the fields of Humanities and Social Sciences, provides financial assistance for the same purpose.

One of the major criticisms for the state universities is connected with quality and relevance of education to secure employment. It was stated that the pattern and content of the state university education system have been largely determined by the needs of the public services of the colonial period, which continued even after regaining independence. As a result, the state university education has not provided the country with a work force ready to face the challenges of a dynamic, market oriented economy (Central Bank of Sri Lanka 2000; World Bank, 2010). Even though technical and professional subjects in the areas of medicine, engineering, general sciences, management and law were introduced to the universities, there was a mismatch between the skill demands of private sector and the supply of universities (Ranasinghe, 1992). Central Bank of Sri Lanka (2000, p. 19) stated that a high unemployment and under employment rate among university graduates points to the mismatch between supply and demand conditions for graduate employment, reflecting a supply driven education system with little relevance to labour market conditions. This is clearly reflected in the distribution of unemployed population by the level of education (Ministry of Education, 2007). At national level, only 4 per cent of the total unemployed labour in 2004 had

education less than 5 years of schooling while 55 per cent of the total unemployed labour had secondary and higher education (urban per cent, rural per cent). This implies that the large majority of unemployed labour are educated but remain deprived of employment opportunities due to the mismatch between the supply of education system and demand of labour market (Ministry of Education, 2007). Employers reported that deficiencies in soft skills such as effective communication, working in teams, problem solving and critical thinking as main reasons for not being hired (Ministry of Education, 2007). The World Bank (2010) elaborated the key features of this situation as:

- a) a considerable proportion of graduates currently fail to meet the employment requirements of the private sector for graduates with good English language, information and communication technology and soft skills;
- b) an inadequately skilled graduate labour force to deliver efficient public services, especially in the poorer areas of the country;
- c) the moderate quality of courses and programs in the majority of higher education institutions;
- d) the absence of a national qualification framework with pathways between the various types of higher education institutions, programmes and courses;
- e) inadequate quality assurance mechanisms for the full state and non-state higher education institutions;
- f) the large proportion of students (nearly 60 per cent) enrolled in external degree programmes with minimal academic support;
- g) the poorer coverage and quality of higher education in lagging regions such as the Northern and Eastern Provinces;
- h) weak research and knowledge linkages between higher education institutions and the industrial and service sectors of the economy; and
- i) the need for higher education institutions to play a prominent role in the social and cultural life of the country, particularly to promote a favourable environment for a peaceful, pluralist and multi-ethnic society.

The Government of Sri Lanka with the assistance of the World Bank introduced two projects to address these issues in the recent past, namely, Improving Relevance and Quality of Undergraduate Education project 2003-2009 and Higher Education for the Twenty First Century project 2011-2015. These two projects are discussed in brief in the section on Higher education reforms.

Establishing and maintaining successful collaborations with industry is a vital role of universities, which brings numerous benefits to universities, industrial firms and to the socio-economic development of the country. Still, the objectives and expectations of universities and industrial firms in Sri Lanka have considerable differences where the state funded universities setting their own academic priorities and firms aim to maximize competitive advantage by pursuing private knowledge. Most existing collaborations state universities maintain with industry are based around student placements in firms as part of the Bachelor's degree programs and the provision of individual consultancy to industrial firms (Malik and Wickramasinghe, 2015). However, it is also apparent that some industrial firms simply remain ignorant as to what universities can provide in terms of new knowledge and support for the firm through research. Similarly, some universities seem to be unaware of the range of different mechanisms available to explore collaborations and interactions with industrial firms (Wickramasinghe and Malik, 2016). According to Wickramasinghe and Malik (2016), the remit of university-industry collaborative projects (e.g. research and development collaboration) might sometimes be too complex to implement in a developing country setting in Sri Lanka. Still, since university-industry interactions in Sri Lanka is a relatively recent phenomenon it has received limited proper leadership and direction or monitoring from within the state university sector. This has led to inadequate performance in research outcomes of higher education sector. With regard to research outcomes in the state universities, 67 PhDs (1 per cent), 129 MPhils (2 per cent), 5518 other postgraduate degrees (97 per cent) were awarded in 2013. Of the PhDs, only 50 per cent (33 of 67) were in pure sciences. Sri Lanka is rated in the 105th position (out of 143 countries) in both innovation index and knowledge economy index rankings in 2012 (Ministry of Technology and Research, 2014). As a country, Sri Lanka is in a very low position in obtaining intellectual patent rights compared to other countries in the Asian region (Ministry of Technology and Research, 2014). Although the majority of state universities have their own scholarly journal publications, annual research conferences and award schemes to popularise research, the research output of Sri Lankan academics in indexed journals were very limited (Ministry of Technology and Research, 2014).

Governance of the state university education in Sri Lanka. The Ministry of Higher education governs the higher education sector of the country. University Grants Commission established in 1978 that comes under this Ministry is responsible for planning, coordinating, and regulating the university education of the country; allocating finance to state governed

universities; maintaining uniform academic standards across state universities; regulating and allocating new intakes for Bachelor's degrees in the state universities based on the capacity of each university and students' performance in the General Certificate of Examination-Advanced Level examination (University Grants Commission, n.d.). The University Grants Commission has a corporate plan for the development of the university sector and all state universities have corporate plans for the development of their institutions.

Higher education reforms in Sri Lanka

Our review led to identify two projects undertaken to reform higher education in the country. The first was the project initiated by the National Education Commission in 1998. The second is the projects initiated with the funding from the World Bank from 2003 to 2015.

National policy framework on university, technical and vocational education. The National Education Commission, which advises the President on education policy, has prepared a national policy framework on university, technical and vocational education (National Education Commission, 2009) in consultation with Ministry of Higher Education, University Grants Commission, Sri Lanka Institute for Advanced Technological Education, and other higher education providers. This is an outcome of two constructive policy dialogues held among policy makers and other stakeholders (including universities, chambers of commerce, federations of employers, community-based organisations, International Development Association, Asian Development Bank and civil society) by National Education Commission in 1996 and by the Presidential Task Force on university education in 1998, with the intention of reforming the higher education in Sri Lanka.

This government's national policy framework for the development of higher education prepared in the year 2009 by National Education Commission seeks to:

- (a) strengthen the quality of graduates and professionals entering the state and private higher education institutions;
- (b) meet the special expansion and quality needs of the Northern and Eastern Provinces of the country;
- (c) promote reconciliation, social cohesion and national unity through research, advocacy, teaching and community services among staff and students from different ethnic and religious groups;
- (d) improve the economic relevance of higher education by promoting skills in demand in the labour market, such as English, information and communication

- technology and soft skills as well as expanding job-oriented higher education programmes in the alternative higher education sector;
- (e) strengthen the governance and policy framework of the higher education sector, with the establishment of Sri Lanka Qualification Framework and quality assurance mechanisms involving both state and private higher education institutions, and all modes of delivery including external degree programmes;
 - (f) improve the quality of higher education institutions, staff, degree programmes, curricula and assessment methods;
 - (g) promote private-public partnerships and private sector involvement in higher education;
 - (h) expand postgraduate education and research;
 - (i) enable higher education institutions to diversify sources of funding including through, among other measures, workplace linkages, commercialisation of intellectual services, technology brokerage offices, and business offices; and
 - (j) diversify the provision of higher education by attracting franchises of overseas higher education institutions, and strengthening open and distance education opportunities.

International Development Association/World Bank. Sri Lankan government has taken steps in recent times to reform higher education sector as a long-term strategy to respond to national concerns by providing vital skills required for the country's social and economic development with the assistance of International Development Association (World Bank, 2003). According to the World Bank (2010), International Development Association is the only development partner with an interest and capacity to assist in achieving Sri Lankan governments' development goals for the higher education sector (World Bank, 2010). To date, International Development Association has been the largest education donor in Sri Lanka. It provided foreign assistance to primary and secondary education through various projects (such as World Bank, 2006, 2011a, 2011b). The World Bank through International Development Association involved in two projects targeted at higher education sector of the country. These projects were Improving Relevance and Quality of Undergraduate Education project 2003-2009 and Higher Education for the Twenty First Century project 2011-2015. These two projects are described below in brief.

The Improving Relevance and Quality of Undergraduate Education Project 2003-2009. This is the World Bank's first involvement in the higher education Sector in the country. The project sought to make attitudinal changes in the higher education system, particularly to bring about greater accountability through quality assurance mechanism and link funding to performance through the competitive funding mechanisms by implementing four initiatives (World Bank, 2010). These were:

- (a) the establishment of a higher education management information system for the universities;
- (b) the development of quality assurance mechanisms for undergraduate education;
- (c) the provision of a small institutional block grant for university development through special programmes to strengthen administration, student services, social harmony, improved English language competency, and computer skills of teachers and graduates; and
- (d) the promotion of competition among higher education institutions of comparable nature by creating a competitive quality enhancement fund targeted at undergraduate degree programmes. For this purpose, grant recipients were tiered into four categories of established state universities, regionally located state universities, conflict-affected state universities, and private institutions and professional organisations (World Bank, 2003, 2010).

The Ministry of Higher Education in collaboration with University Grants Commission served as the main executing agencies for the project.

After the completion of the project, in the year 2010, the World Bank (2010, p. 28) stated that the reforms introduced through Improving Relevance and Quality of Undergraduate Education project 2003-2009 were initially met with resistance but once the benefits of the reforms became evident they gained popularity in the universities. Further, the universities located at the conflict-affected regions and the newly established regional universities particularly benefited from the quality assurance mechanism. Furthermore, the quality enhancement fund gained increasing popularity as the concept of competing for resources through good performance came to be accepted in the university community. In addition, feedback received from stakeholders and beneficiaries, including students, academics and employers from private sector, on these reforms have been positive and favourable, and provided evidence for increasing number of graduates securing jobs in private sector. Specifically, employers from the private sector observed improvements in the

quality of graduates from degree programmes supported by the quality enhancement funds, in comparison to graduates from the same degree programmes prior to the quality enhancement funds. Academics appreciated the opportunities for human resource development, curriculum reform, improved pedagogy, the receipt of modern equipment and technology due to the project, and mechanisms instituted for quality assurance. Feedback from students suggested that skills in information and communication technology and English language acquired through the quality enhancement funds have been very helpful in obtaining jobs in the private and non-government organisations.

Higher education for the twenty first century project 2011-2015. Through this second project, the World Bank sought to broaden and deepen the level of engagement and support by not only involved in Bachelor's level education (like Improving Relevance and Quality of Undergraduate Education project 2003-2009) but also involved in postgraduate education, research, distance education and external degree programmes, and alternative higher education sector of both state and private higher education institutions (World Bank, 2010). Accordingly, the main intentions of the project were to expand Sri Lanka Qualification Framework, quality assurance mechanisms and higher education management information system, which were initiated under Improving Relevance and Quality of Undergraduate Education project 2003-2009. In addition, Higher Education for the Twenty First Century project 2011-2015 supported for human resource development of academic and managerial staff. The Ministry of Higher Education in collaboration with University Grants Commission and Sri Lanka Institute for Advanced Technological Education served as the main executing agencies for the project.

This project was implemented under four phases. In the first phase, Higher Education for the Twenty First Century project 2011-2015 supported national level developments in the establishment of Sri Lanka Qualification Framework and the development of quality assurance mechanism covering the entire higher education sector. Sri Lanka Qualification Framework intended to develop an integrated higher education system with harmonised quality standards and defined linkages to the labour market. Quality assurance mechanisms intended to support improvements in quality standards across the sector and strengthen the sector's governance framework. According to the World Bank (2010), Sri Lanka Qualification Framework was based on its experience in the countries such as Australia, Scotland, Ireland and South Africa while quality assurance mechanisms were based on its experience in Malaysia, Thailand and Tunisia.

In the second phase, Higher Education for the Twenty First Century project 2011-2015 supported to improve the quality of programmes and the employability of graduates through the provision of University Development Grants and Quality and Innovation Grants. University Development Grants aimed to improve the social and economic relevance of university education. Between these two grants, Quality and Innovation Grants was a competitive fund that was made available to selected Faculties and study programmes on a competitive basis while University Development Grants was made available to all universities. For the purpose of Quality and Innovation Grants recipients were tiered into three categories of established state universities, regionally located state universities, and conflict-affected state universities. According to the World Bank (2010), University Development Grants was designed based on its experience in Chile, India, Mauretania, Mozambique, Nigeria and Tanzania. Quality and Innovation Grant aimed to make curriculum reform, modernisation of teaching, learning and assessment methods, innovative activities to improve the employability of graduates, and activities to strengthen university-industry linkages. According to the World Bank (2010), Quality and Innovation Grants drew lessons from competitive funds in Chile, India, Indonesia, Ghana and Vietnam.

In the third phase, Higher Education for the Twenty First Century project 2011-2015 supported the development of alternative higher education sector at technological institutes, which provide more direct job-oriented programmes than programmes in the conventional university sector. It was expected that this phase could directly strengthen the linkages between higher education sector and labour market. According to the World Bank (2010), this phase was designed based on its experience in Chile, India, Mauretania and Tunisia. In the fourth and final phase, Higher Education for the Twenty First Century project 2011-2015 supported to strengthen the qualifications of academic staff of higher education institutions and organisational capacity of the higher education sector. According to the World Bank (2010), this phase was designed based on its experience in Chile and Vietnam.

Conclusions and challenges for the future

This article has provided a review of higher education in state universities in Sri Lanka. The state universities occupy a centre stage in the country's higher education system. An attempt has been made in this article to provide an understanding of the comprehensiveness of the state funded free university education that is connected to a public-welfare system, its fundamental values such as equity, strategies adopted and relationship among key governing actors.

The achievements of two recent projects implemented in the higher education sector will become evident in years to come. Still, state universities of the country face major problems relating to access to education, quality and relevance for employment opportunities. The state universities have to continue addressing this mismatch between skills acquired through the education system and the requirements of labour market and society. This mismatch exists in cognitive and non-cognitive skills domains, specifically, disciplined work ethic, capacity to work with others in a team, a problem solving approach, creativity, initiative, flexibility, adaptability, drive and communication skills (Ministry of Education, 2007). The needs of addressing these skills are not an issue faced by Sri Lanka alone. Previous research such as Dyllick (2015) and Hall et al. (2013) also emphasised the importance of these skills to succeed in day-to-day work tasks. Therefore, state universities have to equip their graduates with sufficient academic and practical skills to fit into the world of work by improving the quality and relevance of education. The country has witnessed a rapid increase in its knowledge-based economy over the last two decades. Interventions to reduce the skill mismatch will lead to create employment opportunities for the educated labour at a much faster rate compared to the past.

Further, in the contemporary world, equipping labour force with capabilities to be employable may not be sufficient. They may need capabilities to upgrade their skills continuously for future employability. In other words, higher education institutions should be capable of creating life-long learners. Therefore, in response, state universities need to be more flexible and offer part-time, evening and weekend programmes for these learners. For the successful delivery of programs integration with distance learning mode may become an option. Accordingly, quality assurance systems should be broadened to incorporate life-long learning as well.

Furthermore, the strengthened relationship between universities and alternative higher education institutions, industry and society will benefit the country immensely. According to Hall et al. (2013) the achievement of economic goals of a county expects higher education sector to respond to productivity agenda, innovation agenda and contribute to improvements in management capabilities. During the recent past, Sri Lankan governments emphasized an agenda of productivity growth and innovation (Ministry of Technology and Research, 2014). One of the drivers to achieve this schema would be to investment in skills of current and future labour force. Therefore, forums and future projects for the development of higher education of the country involving key stakeholders would be highly beneficial.

In addition, Sri Lanka experienced that budgetary financing as a means of funding the state university education restricts the relevance and quality of higher education over the last decades. This resulted in the engagement of International Development Association for the development of higher education sector. The two projects implemented so far have shown favourable benefits making higher education institutions innovative, responsive, integrated and engaged compared to the past. However, as stated by the World Bank (2010):

The development interventions supported by the Higher Education for the Twenty First Century project 2011-2015 follow international best practices from the Bank's engagement in higher education in a number of countries around the world. In addition, the project builds upon the lessons learned from International Development Association's past education interventions in Sri Lanka. (World Bank, 2010, p. 17)

It can be argued that future such projects may lead to identify a distinctively Sri Lankan path which better suits in creating values needed to live in peace and social harmony and respect for diversity in a multi-cultural society.

Finally, although the country achieved notable gains in literacy, universal primary education and gender equity in education, state universities has to increase the access to education. World Bank reports that "higher education represents an important avenue for social mobility in Sri Lanka" (2003, p. 22) and "despite graduate unemployment, which does not spare Sri Lanka, higher education still yields positive private and social returns" (2010, p. 17). The increasing demand for higher education, which can be seen clearly by the magnitude of the difference between the number of eligible students and the actual number admitted to different academic programmes in state universities, should be viewed against the low government expenditure on the university education. The competitiveness for higher education has adversely affected the expectations of average students. Those who are privileged to pursue higher education in Sri Lanka are a magnitude when compared to the other countries of interest for Sri Lankan economic policy. Therefore, initiatives are need to increase the access to higher education, especially, to state universities.

Areas for future research. This paper was based on the secondary sources of information available on the topic concerned. However, a complete evaluation of the conduct of state universities requires investigations into how the system changed to address quality in teaching and learning. The lack of availability of secondary sources on quality and relevance of higher education put some limits on the content of the paper. Therefore, future research

could evaluate curriculum, learning materials, delivery, evaluation and monitoring of processes, and the availability and competency of teachers. Further, investigations on the perspectives of stakeholders (i.e., graduates, employers and society) may broaden the understanding of relevance of education. Further, state universities have a key role to play in research and development and university-industry collaborations. Investigations into these areas are currently lacking in the higher education sector. Furthermore, future studies could investigate interactions between universities and alternative higher education institutions of the state and private sectors. Therefore, future research in these areas using different research approaches such as surveys and case studies will be able to deepen the understanding and may become valuable in policy making.

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